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Corrosion Inhibition of S275 Carbon Steel in CO₂ Capture Systems Using Monoethanolamine (MEA) Solvent

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ABSTRACT

Corrosion in CO₂ capture units significantly impacts safety and costs. This study evaluates S275 carbon steel in CO₂-loaded monoethanolamine (MEA) as a cost-effective alternative to 316 L stainless steel, testing various inhibitors: methionine, imidazole, sodium sulfite, sodium metavanadate (NaVO₃), and copper(II) sulfate (CuSO₄). Corrosion performance is assessed using potentiodynamic polarization and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS), while SEM and confocal microscopy analyze surface mechanisms. Results show that NaVO₃ and CuSO₄ provide the highest protection, reaching inhibition efficiencies of 94% (750 ppm) and 98% (1000 ppm), respectively. Polarization curves indicate that both inhibitors act as anodic inhibitors by forming protective layers. SEM confirm iron-based oxides in NaVO₃-treated samples and mixed copper-iron oxides in CuSO₄-treated ones. Overall, S275 steel shows high potential for CO₂ capture systems when paired with effective inhibitors.

1 | Introduction

Corrosion of metallic materials is considered one of the most critical challenges in CO₂ capture units [1], particularly under elevated operating temperatures and in the presence of acid gases, impurities, and amine degradation products [2–4]. Corrosion poses significant operational challenges, affecting both plant safety and economic performance through increased maintenance demands, unplanned downtime, and production losses [5]. Carbon steel is currently the primary material used for piping in CO₂ capture units due to its favorable mechanical properties and relatively low cost [6]; however, its high corrosion rates often lead to increased maintenance requirements that must be carefully considered. Stainless steels provide enhanced corrosion resistance, yet they do not completely eliminate corrosion-related risks and are associated with substantially higher material and

fabrication costs [2], which limits their widespread application, particularly in large-scale industrial installations.

Addressing these challenges requires a comprehensive understanding of the underlying degradation mechanisms and the factors that govern their progression [7]. To date, two primary approaches have been widely investigated for corrosion control: the selection of amine solvents with inherently lower corrosivity and the use of corrosion inhibitors to mitigate metal degradation under aggressive operating conditions [2]. Among the available mitigation strategies, corrosion inhibitors are considered highly effective, operationally practical, and economically viable for protecting metals and alloys in corrosive environments [8, 9].

Corrosion inhibitors are substances or mixtures that, at low concentrations, mitigate metal degradation either by promoting

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the formation of a protective surface layer or by modifying the primary reactions responsible for corrosion [10]. They can be broadly categorized based on their chemical composition and mode of action [11]. Chemically, inhibitors are classified as organic, inorganic, or hybrid [12]. Organic inhibitors often contain heteroatoms such as nitrogen, oxygen, or sulfur, which facilitate adsorption onto the metal surface and the formation of a protective film [11, 13]. Inorganic inhibitors generally include metal salts or oxides that react with the substrate to form a barrier against corrosive species [10]. Hybrid inhibitors combine features of both types to enhance protection under aggressive conditions. Based on their mode of action, inhibitors are classified as anodic, cathodic, or mixed-type. Anodic inhibitors decrease the anodic reaction rate by promoting surface passivation, cathodic inhibitors suppress reduction reactions either through surface adsorption or by competing with the oxidizing species for electrons [14], while mixed-type inhibitors influence both anodic and cathodic processes, providing comprehensive protection in complex environments.

Carbon steel is a widely used engineering material, making corrosion inhibition essential. Vanadium-based inhibitors such as NaVO_3 reduce corrosion in MEA and AMP-MEA systems [15], while metavanadates are effective in acidic chloride media [16]. Copper-based compounds like CuCO_3 also provide strong protection in amine-based CO_2 absorption systems [2, 17]. Sodium sulfite (Na_2SO_3) acts as an oxygen scavenger, lowering corrosion rates in aqueous and amine solutions [5, 18]. Organic inhibitors, particularly amines with heteroatoms (N, S, O, P), protect by adsorbing on metal surfaces [8, 19, 20]. However, their comparative performance in amine systems and across different steels remains insufficiently explored.

In this study, the corrosion behavior of S275 carbon steel in CO_2 -loaded MEA amine solutions containing corrosion inhibitors is systematically investigated using electrochemical techniques at 25°C . Specifically, potentiodynamic polarization and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) are employed to evaluate inhibitor efficiency and to assess whether their application can enable the use of carbon steel as a viable alternative to 316 L stainless steel without compromising corrosion resistance. In addition, surface characterization by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and energy-dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) is performed to examine the corroded surfaces and to gain insights into the underlying corrosion inhibition mechanisms. The findings of this work are expected to provide valuable guidance for material selection and cost reduction in industrial processes involving amine-based systems.

2 | Materials and Methods

2.1 | Tested Materials and Solutions

For the electrochemical measurements, S275 carbon steel samples are prepared by cutting a commercial plate into specimens measuring $20\text{ mm} \times 10\text{ mm} \times 2.5\text{ mm}$. The nominal composition of the carbon steel is given in Table 1. Before each experiment, the sample surfaces are prepared by stepwise grinding using SiC abrasive papers, employing grit sizes ranging from 80 to 1200 for carbon steel. Following surface preparation, the specimens are rinsed with deionized water and ethanol and

TABLE 1 | Chemical composition of S275 carbon steel used in experiments.

composition (%wt.)	C	Mn	Si	P	S	Fe
S275	0.25	1.6	0.05	0.04	0.05	Bal.

then dried to ensure the removal of any remaining surface contaminants. Finally, the exposed surface area of each specimen is measured using a vernier caliper.

Monoethanolamine (MEA) solvents are prepared by mixing high-purity monoethanolamine (99 wt.%) with deionized water to achieve a final amine concentration of 30 wt.%. Controlled CO_2 absorption is then carried out to reach a loading of 0.5 mol CO_2 /mol MEA.

2.2 | Tested Corrosion Inhibitors

Following sample preparation, inhibitor solutions are prepared by adding reagent-grade inhibitors, used as received without further purification, to CO_2 -loaded MEA solutions. Pre-determined amounts of each inhibitor are dissolved in 50 mL of solvent, and the resulting mixtures are stirred for approximately 30 min until homogeneous solutions are obtained. Multiple corrosion inhibitors are investigated at various concentrations. Sodium metavanadate (NaVO_3), copper(II) sulfate (CuSO_4), sodium sulfite (Na_2SO_3), methionine ($\text{C}_5\text{H}_{11}\text{NO}_2\text{S}$), and imidazole ($\text{C}_3\text{H}_4\text{N}_2$) are selected based on a review of the relevant literature. Sodium metavanadate and imidazole are supplied by Thermo Fisher Scientific (Waltham, MA, USA), copper(II) sulfate by J&K Scientific (San Jose, CA, USA) and sodium sulfite by Th. Geyer (Renningen, Germany), and methionine by BLD Pharm (Shanghai, China).

2.3 | Electrochemical Experiments

All of the electrochemical studies are conducted using a three-electrode cell, with a saturated calomel electrode (SCE) as reference and a platinum rod as counter electrode, controlled by a 1010E potentiostat (Gamry Instruments, USA). The experiments are conducted at atmospheric pressure at room temperature 25°C , chosen to simulate industrial CO_2 -capture operating environments. Data analysis is performed using Gamry Echem Analyst software supplied with the potentiostat. Each test is repeated at least three times to ensure reproducibility and data consistency.

Prior to each electrochemical experiment, the open circuit potential (OCP) is monitored for 1 h to ensure system stabilization. Potentiodynamic polarization measurements are conducted by scanning the electrode potential from -300 to $+1000\text{ mV}$ relative to the SCE reference electrode at a scan rate of $2\text{ mV}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$. The resulting polarization curves are analyzed using the Tafel extrapolation method to determine the corrosion potential (E_{corr}), corrosion current density (i_{corr}), and corrosion rate. EIS measurements are performed at the stabilized OCP

(E_{OCP}), over a frequency range from 100 kHz to 100 mHz, using a sinusoidal perturbation amplitude of 10 mV.

The inhibition efficiency (η) of the tested corrosion inhibitor is calculated by using Equation 1 given below [21]:

$$\eta(\text{PP}) = \frac{i_{\text{corr}}^0 - i_{\text{corr}}}{i_{\text{corr}}^0} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

where i_{corr}^0 and i_{corr} are the corrosion current density in the absence and presence of inhibitor, respectively.

3 | Results and Discussion

3.1 | Potentiodynamic Polarization Tests

Various concentrations of each corrosion inhibitor are investigated, and the corresponding corrosion rates are summarized in Figure 1. For clarity, only the polarization curves corresponding to the most effective conditions—defined as those yielding a corrosion rate reduction greater than one order of magnitude

relative to the uninhibited solution—are presented. The corrosion current density is determined by Tafel extrapolation of the cathodic branches only (Figure 1), as the anodic branches lack sufficiently linear regions.

The results show that methionine, imidazole and sodium sulfite do not significantly reduce the corrosion rate of S275 carbon steel. In contrast, NaVO_3 at 750 and 1000 ppm and CuSO_4 at 250, 500, and 1000 ppm produce a substantial reduction, exceeding one order of magnitude. The lowest rate ($9.38 \mu\text{m}/\text{year}$) is obtained for CuSO_4 at 1000 ppm.

Methionine inhibits corrosion through sulfur-assisted adsorption and the formation of a protective surface film [8], whereas imidazole, a nitrogen-containing heterocyclic compound, adsorbs onto the metal surface through its nitrogen atoms and aromatic ring [19]. Their limited performance is likely due to insufficient surface coverage at the tested concentrations, while higher concentrations are avoided to prevent impurity effects.

Sodium sulfite acts mainly as an oxygen scavenger, reducing the cathodic oxygen reduction reaction. Although a slight decrease

FIGURE 1 | Corrosion rates of S275 carbon steel in CO₂-loaded MEA solutions at 25°C with different inhibitors and concentrations. The figure also shows the corrosion rates obtained from Tafel extrapolation based on cathodic polarization data. [Color figure can be viewed at [wileyonlinelibrary.com](https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/maco.70196)]

in corrosion rate is observed (notably at 500 ppm), the effect remains limited, suggesting that oxygen reduction is not the dominant cathodic process in this system.

The addition of both inhibitors significantly alters the polarization behavior compared with the blank solution. A clear shift in the corrosion potential is observed, accompanied by a notable change in the potential range of the passivation region. In the uninhibited solution, passivation occurs in two distinct stages: the first between -500 and -400 mV and the second between -300 and 200 mV. According to the iron–water Pourbaix diagram at 25°C (Figure 3a) and the measured pH values (Figure 2d), the first stage is associated with the formation of Fe_3O_4 , while the second corresponds to the formation of FeOOH [22]. In addition to passive film formation through electrochemical reactions involving the inhibitor anions on the steel surface, the positive shift of the polarization curves moves the Fe stability region toward conditions where FeOOH is the dominant phase in the Pourbaix diagram. As FeOOH is a highly stable corrosion product, its formation contributes to improved corrosion resistance.

As illustrated in Figure 2a, the addition of NaVO_3 at concentrations of 750 and 1000 ppm shifts the polarization curves toward more noble corrosion potentials and significantly decreases primarily anodic and cathodic current densities. The displacement of E_{corr} exceeds 85 mV relative to the uninhibited system, indicating that NaVO_3 predominantly acts as an anodic inhibitor [23]. Although the overall polarization behavior at the two concentrations is comparable, the solution containing 750 ppm NaVO_3 exhibits slightly lower anodic and cathodic

current densities, suggesting marginally superior inhibition efficiency at this concentration. The absence of further improvement at 1000 ppm implies that the optimal inhibitor concentration is approximately 750 ppm; Beyond this level, further addition of NaVO_3 does not lead to a significant enhancement in corrosion protection, likely because a stable protective film has already formed on the metal surface, and any excess inhibitor may remain undissolved in the amine solution.

The anodic polarization curves in the presence of NaVO_3 (Figure 2a) can be divided into three regions. Region I (-300 to $+200$ mV) corresponds to active dissolution of the steel, followed by a pseudopassive region (Region II, $+200$ to $+800$ mV), where current density becomes nearly independent of potential due to the formation of a partially protective surface film. Based on the pH of the CO_2 -loaded MEA solutions (Figure 2d) and the vanadium–water Pourbaix diagram of Figure 3c [24], vanadium is expected to exist mainly as HVO_4^{2-} . These species interact with Fe^{2+} ions, promoting iron vanadate formation and contributing to pseudopassivity. In addition, VO_3^- species can act as mild oxidizing agents, facilitating the oxidation of Fe^{2+} to Fe^{3+} , which precipitates as Fe_2O_3 or FeOOH —more stable and less soluble compounds than Fe^{2+} -based oxides, enhancing film protectiveness [26]. At potentials above $+800$ mV, a transition to the transpassive region (Region III) occurs, likely due to film breakdown and/or oxygen evolution [27].

For CuSO_4 (Figure 2b), polarization curves exhibit similar shapes across all concentrations, indicating a consistent inhibition mechanism. Increasing CuSO_4 concentration reduces

FIGURE 2 | Potentiodynamic polarization behavior of S275 carbon steel in CO_2 -loaded MEA solutions with the most effective inhibitors. (a) Polarization curves in the presence of NaVO_3 at various concentrations. (b) Polarization curves in the presence of CuSO_4 at various concentrations. (c) Corresponding inhibition efficiency (η) for all tested conditions. (d) Measured pH values of the investigated solutions. [Color figure can be viewed at [wileyonlinelibrary.com](https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com)]

FIGURE 3 | Pourbaix diagrams of (a) the Fe–H₂O system, (b) the Cu–H₂O system at 25°C [22, 24, 25] and (c) the V–H₂O system. The Pourbaix of Fe–H₂O system is adapted from [Fioravante, Igor and Nunes, Ronaldo and Acciari, Heloisa and Codaro, Eduardo], [Journal of the Brazilian Chemical Society, 2019], of V–H₂O system is adapted from [Hari Jammulamadaka and Sarma V. Pisupati], [Journal of Fuels, 2023], licensed under CC BY [22, 24]. [Color figure can be viewed at [wileyonlinelibrary.com](https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com)]

FIGURE 4 | Schematic illustration of the proposed corrosion inhibition mechanisms of (a) NaVO₃ and (b) CuSO₄ on S275 carbon steel in CO₂-loaded MEA solutions. [Color figure can be viewed at [wileyonlinelibrary.com](https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com)]

both anodic and cathodic current densities and shifts E_{CORR} to more noble values, confirming predominantly anodic behavior. At 250–500 ppm, five regions are identified, including two pseudopassive zones. The first is attributed to Cu²⁺ reduction to Cu⁰ via galvanic displacement, forming a protective copper layer, while the second involves CuO deposition, further inhibiting anodic reactions. This interpretation is supported by the corresponding pH measurements and the copper–water Pourbaix diagram shown in Figures 2d and 3b. At 1000 ppm, only the higher-potential pseudopassive region is observed. The decrease in passive current density with increasing concentration indicates enhanced film formation.

Although the inhibition performance of both NaVO₃ and CuSO₄ is predominantly anodic, as demonstrated by the pronounced decrease in anodic current densities relative to the uninhibited CO₂-loaded MEA solution, measurable changes are also observed in the cathodic branches, indicating that both compounds affect both the anodic and cathodic reaction kinetics. For CuSO₄, the reduction of Cu²⁺ ions (Cu²⁺ + 2e⁻ → Cu⁰) results in the deposition of metallic copper on cathodic areas of the steel surface. This deposited copper partially blocks cathodic active sites, thereby suppressing cathodic reactions and contributing to the overall inhibition efficiency. For NaVO₃, the observed slight reduction in cathodic current density can likely be attributed to the formation of a protective surface film that partially blocks both anodic and cathodic active sites. To facilitate a clearer understanding of the corrosion inhibition mechanisms of both inhibitors, a schematic representation is presented in Figure 4.

Overall, the calculated inhibition efficiencies show that both NaVO₃ and CuSO₄ provide excellent corrosion protection across all tested concentrations, with values exceeding 90% and reaching a maximum of approximately 98% for CuSO₄ at 1000 ppm. The corresponding corrosion rate for this system is approximately 9 μm/year (Table 2), slightly lower than that of SS 316 L in CO₂-loaded MEA solution reported in our previous work (10 μm/year) [28], indicating that CuSO₄ enables S275 carbon steel to achieve corrosion resistance comparable to, or even slightly better than, stainless steel. These results imply that, with optimized inhibitor dosing, S275 could serve as a cost-effective alternative to SS 316 L in CO₂-rich environments, although additional protective measures may be required for long-term service. Also, these corrosion rate values (lower than 30 μm/year) indicate an excellent performance under such alkaline environments, highlighting the strong inhibitory action of the tested compounds and their suitability for mitigating corrosion in CO₂-containing systems.

3.2 | Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy Tests and Equivalent Circuits

Figure 5 presents the EIS results, including Bode magnitude and phase angle plots as well as Nyquist diagrams, obtained for both inhibited and uninhibited MEA solutions at 25°C. In addition, Figure 6 illustrates the equivalent electrical circuits employed to model the corrosion processes, while Table 3 summarizes the corresponding fitting parameters derived from the analysis.

TABLE 2 | Electrochemical parameters of S275 carbon steel immersed in CO₂-loaded MEA solution at 25°C, in the absence and presence of corrosion inhibitors: corrosion potential (E_{corr}), corrosion current density (i_{corr}), cathodic Tafel slope (β_c), and corrosion rate. Values represent the average of three independent measurements.

Inhibitor and concentration	E_{corr} (mV vs SCE)	i_{corr} ($\mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$)	β_c (mV)	β_a (mV)	Corrosion rate ($\mu\text{m}/\text{year}$)
Without inhibitor	-785.4	46.7	436.5	—	542.1
NaVO ₃ -750 ppm	-303.3	2.1	130.3	—	24.2
NaVO ₃ -1000 ppm	-286.4	2.5	124	—	29.2
CuSO ₄ -250 ppm	-188.1	4.2	189.9	—	48.8
CuSO ₄ -500 ppm	-173.1	3.7	183.5	—	42.9
CuSO ₄ -1000 ppm	-212.9	0.8	186.8	—	9.4

FIGURE 5 | Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) analysis of S275 steel in CO₂-loaded MEA solutions at 25°C in the presence of varying concentrations of CuSO₄ and NaVO₃ inhibitors: (a) Bode magnitude plots, (b) Nyquist plots, and (c) Bode phase angle plots. [Color figure can be viewed at [wileyonlinelibrary.com](https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com)]

FIGURE 6 | Equivalent electrical circuit models used to represent the CO₂-loaded MEA solutions under (a) uninhibited and (b) inhibited conditions. [Color figure can be viewed at [wileyonlinelibrary.com](https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com)]

TABLE 3 | Calculated parameters of the equivalent circuit elements (Figure 6) used to model the corrosion behavior of S275 carbon steel in CO₂-loaded MEA solutions, both in the absence and presence of inhibitors, at 25°C.

Type of inhibitor	R_s (Ω)	R_{ct} ($10^4 \Omega \cdot \text{cm}^2$)	L ($\text{H} \cdot \text{cm}^2$)	n_{dl}	CPE_{dl} ($10^{-5} \text{S} \cdot \text{s}^a / \text{cm}^2$)	R_{dep} ($\Omega \cdot \text{cm}^2$)	n_{dep}	CPE_{dep} ($10^{-5} \text{S} \cdot \text{s}^a / \text{cm}^2$)	χ^2 (10^{-3})
without inhibitor	17	0.0036	149	0.33	1040	523	0.82	22.5	0.16
NaVO ₃ -750 ppm	20.9	6.1	—	0.89	4.5	19.8	0.98	2.7	0.98
NaVO ₃ -1,000 ppm	27.6	4.9	—	0.88	5.5	13.7	0.98	2.7	0.85
CuSO ₄ -250 ppm	1.1	5.1	—	0.94	5.1	11.6	0.16	4.2	0.88
CuSO ₄ -500 ppm	22.5	5.8	—	0.71	2.8	40	0.99	2.2	2.4
CuSO ₄ -1000 ppm	17	9.7	—	0.88	2.8	18	1	1.6	1.05

The Bode magnitude plots for all inhibited solutions (Figure 5a) exhibit similar shapes, indicating that the corrosion mechanism remains unchanged. In the high-frequency region, the curves reach a plateau corresponding to the solution resistance (R_{sol}) [29], with only minor differences observed between uninhibited and inhibited solutions. In the medium-frequency range, capacitive behavior is evident, reflecting the formation of a stable double layer and/or protective surface film [30]. At low frequencies, the impedance approaches a plateau, indicating stabilized resistance values and suggesting the presence of a protective layer. The low-frequency impedance magnitude serves as an indicator of corrosion resistance, with higher values corresponding to improved protection. All inhibited solutions display resistances over two orders of magnitude higher than the uninhibited solution, with CuSO₄ at 1000 ppm achieving the highest inhibition efficiency.

The Nyquist plot of the uninhibited CO₂-loaded MEA solution (Figure 5b) shows a depressed semicircle in the high frequency region and a low frequency inductive loop. Previous studies have confirmed that the presence of this inductive loop is linked with pitting corrosion and dynamic changes in the thickness and surface coverage of the protective film during this stage [31, 32]. In contrast, all inhibited solutions display depressed and incomplete semicircles. As the diameter of the semicircle is directly related to the charge transfer resistance, these observations confirm the enhanced corrosion protection provided by the inhibitors. Accordingly, the corrosion resistance decreases in the following order: CuSO₄ (1000 ppm) > NaVO₃ (750 ppm) > CuSO₄ (500 ppm) > NaVO₃ (1000 ppm) > CuSO₄ (250 ppm) > uninhibited solution.

Examination of the Bode phase plots for all solutions tested (Figure 5c) reveals two distinct time constants, one appearing at medium frequencies and the other at low frequencies, suggesting the presence of two different electrochemical processes. These processes may be associated with protective surface layer formation and active corrosion, respectively. At high frequencies, the phase angle approaches 0°, corresponding to the solution resistance [33]. In the medium-frequency range, the phase angle of the inhibited solutions approaches -85°, indicating capacitive behavior associated with the formation of a passive film [34, 35]. Yet the deflection from -90° suggests that the protective layer is permeable to ions [36]. In contrast, the phase angle for the uninhibited solution approaches -50°, suggesting the presence of a less protective surface layer.

The interpretation of the EIS results obtained for the carbon steel specimens is performed through numerical fitting using the equivalent circuits presented in Figure 6. In the inhibited solutions, the equivalent circuit consists of the solution resistance (R_s), a branch representing the active corrosion processes at the exposed metal surface, characterized by the charge transfer resistance and double-layer capacitance (R_{ct} and CPE_{dl}), and a second branch corresponding to areas of the metal substrate covered by corrosion products. This latter branch includes a resistance and a capacitance element (R_{dep} and CPE_{dep}), representing the electrical response of the corrosion deposit layer. The circuit for the uninhibited solution has a similar configuration, with the addition of an inductor in the branch referring to pitting corrosion, or to physically adsorbed chemical species, ions or molecules at the interface of the electrochemical double layer [37]. In both circuits, the pure capacitors are replaced by constant phase elements, due to the non-ideal capacitive response of the electrochemical double layer formed at the metal–electrolyte interface, associated with surface heterogeneities and roughness [34].

The impedance of the CPEs is given by Equation 2:

$$Z_{\text{CPE}} = Y_0^{-1}(j\omega)^{-n}, \quad (2)$$

where Y_0 is the CPE constant, ω is the angular frequency ($\omega = 2\pi f$), n is the CPE exponent describing the deviation from ideal capacitive behavior, and j is the imaginary unit [38]. The accuracy of the fitting procedure is evaluated using the χ^2 parameter. In this study, a χ^2 value on the order of 10^{-3} is adopted as the acceptance criterion, ensuring that only fits exhibiting minimal deviation from the experimental data are considered valid. In addition, the consistency of the impedance data is verified using Kramers–Kronig validation tests carried out with Echem Analyst software.

As shown in Table 3, the addition of both NaVO₃ and CuSO₄ leads to an increase in R_{ct} by more than four orders of magnitude, indicating a marked reduction in corrosion rate due to fewer active sites available for charge transfer and kinetically hindered electrochemical reactions. In contrast, the extremely low R_{ct} values ($36 \Omega \cdot \text{cm}^2$) observed for the uninhibited solution are attributed to both anodic dissolution and pitting corrosion on the carbon steel surface, while the comparatively higher R_{ct} (more than $4.9 \cdot 10^4 \Omega \cdot \text{cm}^2$) in the inhibited solutions indicates that the inhibitors effectively suppress pitting. At the same time,

the double-layer capacitance (C_{dl}) in the inhibited solutions is consistently remarkably lower than in the blank, likely due to partial coverage of the metal surface by corrosion products and/or adsorption of inhibitor molecules that replace previously adsorbed species, thereby modifying the dielectric properties of the double layer and reducing the capacitance [39].

3.3 | Microstructural Characterization of the Samples Using Scanning Electron Microscopy

Electrochemical corrosion tests are complemented by microstructural observations of the samples to better evaluate the extent of material degradation and to correlate the composition of surface deposits with the underlying corrosion mechanisms. The initial microstructure of the carbon steel S275 is also presented for reasons of comparison. Figure 7 illustrates the microstructure of the as-received and corroded specimens following exposure to CO₂-loaded MEA solutions.

Figure 7a shows that the initial microstructure of S275 exhibits a typical ferrite–pearlite microstructure, consisting of equiaxed ferrite grains (dark regions) forming a continuous matrix, within which pearlitic colonies (light regions) are uniformly distributed.

After polarization testing in CO₂-loaded MEA solution, the surface morphology of S275 changes significantly, revealing the formation of various corrosion products. White, amorphous corrosion deposits are observed across the surface; however, they do not form a fully continuous layer. EDS analysis indicates that these deposits are primarily composed of iron, oxygen, and carbon. According to the literature, such corrosion products are likely associated with the formation of siderite (FeCO₃) due to the presence of dissolved CO₂ in the amine

solution [40], as well as iron oxides or hydroxides, such as Fe(OH)₂, Fe₂O₃, and FeOOH [41].

In addition, distinct darker regions are evident, corresponding to the formation of a thin surface film. This film may be attributed to the adsorption of amine molecules onto the metal surface and/or to complex reactions between MEA and the steel substrate, leading to the development of an interfacial layer [42].

Figures 8 and 9 show the surface morphology of carbon steel specimens after polarization tests in the inhibited solutions, highlighting the effect of the inhibitors on surface degradation and film formation.

Examination of the surface of the NaVO₃-inhibited specimens at high magnifications reveals the presence of corrosion precipitates similar in nature to those observed in the uninhibited CO₂-loaded MEA solution. Notably, the dark surface films appear significantly less extensive compared to the uninhibited condition, suggesting that NaVO₃ may suppress or alter the interaction between amine molecules and the metal substrate. Furthermore, EDS analysis does not detect vanadium-containing precipitates on the surface. This observation implies that the primary inhibition mechanism is unlikely to involve the direct formation of vanadium-based surface compounds. Instead, the protective effect of NaVO₃ may be associated with its oxidizing character, promoting the formation and stabilization of iron oxide layers through the oxidative action of VO₃⁻ species.

The primary corrosion products observed on the S275 sample treated with 1000 ppm CuSO₄ are classified into two categories: (i) iron oxides or complexes, and (ii) copper-containing deposits, as confirmed by EDS analysis. Copper-containing precipitates also contain iron, likely originating from the underlying carbon

FIGURE 7 | (a) Initial microstructure and (b,c) microstructures of S275 carbon steel after corrosion in CO₂-loaded MEA solution. [Color figure can be viewed at [wileyonlinelibrary.com](https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/maco.70196)]

FIGURE 8 | SEM micrographs of the corroded specimens after exposure to CO₂-loaded MEA solution containing NaVO₃ (750 ppm): (a) low-magnification image and (b,c) high-magnification images. [Color figure can be viewed at [wileyonlinelibrary.com](https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/maco.70196)]

FIGURE 9 | SEM micrographs of the corroded specimens after exposure to CO₂-loaded MEA solution containing CuSO₄ (1000 ppm): (a) low-magnification image and (b,c) high-magnification images. [Color figure can be viewed at [wileyonlinelibrary.com](https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/maco.70196)]

steel substrate, and appear as a thin, relatively uniform layer on the surface. The formation of copper oxides indicates that CuSO₄ inhibits corrosion primarily by creating a copper-based passive film that blocks further metal dissolution. This protective effect is consistent with the reduction in corrosion current density observed in the polarization curves discussed in subsection 3.1.

3.4 | Surface Characterization by Optical Profilometry

To better assess the corrosion products deposited on the metal substrate, optical profilometry measurements are performed on the corroded samples (after potentiodynamic polarization), both in the presence and absence of inhibitors, in order to determine the

surface roughness (R_a) and examine the general surface characteristics of the substrate. For comparison purposes, the surface of the initial sample, after grinding with 1200-grit paper, is also analyzed. The scratches generated during grinding are observed to have a distinct directional orientation. Therefore, to ensure consistent and reliable roughness evaluation, the roughness parameters are calculated in the direction perpendicular to the grinding direction. The corresponding profilometry images and the calculated surface roughness values are shown in Figure 10.

In the case of the initial sample, the surface reveals the presence of generally smooth grinding lines. In contrast, the surface of

the sample corroded in the uninhibited solution does not exhibit clear signs of grinding; instead, an irregular surface profile is observed, along with several spots indicating the occurrence of pitting corrosion (Figure 10e). The surface roughness of the initial sample is $R_a = 0.055 \mu\text{m}$. After corrosion in the blank CO_2 -loaded MEA solution, a significant increase in roughness is observed, reaching a value of $0.09 \mu\text{m}$ (Figure 10a). This increase can be attributed to uniform corrosion as well as to the deposition of corrosion products that are unevenly distributed on the carbon steel substrate, forming poorly compact layers that are unable to adequately protect the material from further corrosion.

FIGURE 10 | Surface roughness measurements are presented for (a) the initial sample and the sample corroded in an uninhibited CO_2 -loaded MEA solution, as well as for samples corroded in solutions containing inhibitors: (b) NaVO_3 and (c) CuSO_4 . Panel (d) provides a comparative overview of all examined cases. Panel (e) shows optical profilometry images of all samples before and after corrosion, highlighting the effects of CO_2 -loaded MEA solution in the absence and presence of NaVO_3 and CuSO_4 inhibitors. [Color figure can be viewed at [wileyonlinelibrary.com](https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com)]

In the case of the inhibited solutions, the presence of grinding lines on the surface indicates that corrosion is less severe. The calculated roughness values (Figure 10b,c) confirm this observation, as the R_a values are significantly lower than those measured for the uninhibited solution and, in all cases, are also lower than that of the initial non-corroded sample. The reduced surface roughness can be attributed to the formation of dense and compact corrosion product layers that provide enhanced protection to the steel surface.

Overall, the surface topography of the corrosion products deposited on the steel suggests that lower roughness values correspond to surfaces where corrosion products are uniformly distributed, forming flat, compact, and protective layers. In contrast, higher roughness values are associated with surfaces where the corrosion products are unevenly distributed and form poorly compact layers.

4 | Conclusions

This study evaluates the corrosion behavior of carbon steel S275 in CO₂-loaded monoethanolamine (MEA) solutions in the presence of selected corrosion inhibitors. The objective is to determine whether, through appropriate inhibitor selection, S275 can attain corrosion resistance comparable to stainless steel 316 L under identical conditions.

The results show that both NaVO₃ and CuSO₄ provide inhibition efficiencies exceeding 90%. NaVO₃ at 750 ppm achieves an efficiency of 94%, corresponding to a corrosion rate of 27.8 μm/year. Superior performance is obtained with CuSO₄ at 1000 ppm, which reaches an inhibition efficiency of 98.3% and reduces the corrosion rate to 9.4 μm/year, slightly below that measured for 316 L (10 μm/year). Under these optimized conditions, S275 demonstrates corrosion resistance comparable to 316 L. These findings highlight the potential use of carbon steel as a construction material, offering significant cost savings compared to stainless steel and making it a more economically viable alternative.

Author Contributions

Conceptualization: Fani Stergioudi and Nikolaos Michailidis. Methodology: Fani Stergioudi and Evie Nessi. Software: Eleni Lamprou. Validation: Eleni Lamprou and Fani Stergioudi. Formal analysis: Eleni Lamprou. Investigation: Georgios Skordaris and Eleni Lamprou. Resources: Nikolaos Michailidis. Data curation: Georgios Skordaris and Eleni Lamprou. Writing – original draft preparation, Eleni Lamprou and Fani Stergioudi. Writing – review and editing: Fani Stergioudi. Visualization: Eleni Lamprou. Supervision: Nikolaos Michailidis. Project administration: Athanasios I. Papadopoulos. Funding acquisition: A.I.P. Panagiotis Seferlis. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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